

The Grande Cour in marble

Originally this space consisted of a set of old gardens and stables which were reconstructed by Ba Hmad.

It is the most remarkable work of the architect Muhammad Ben Mekki Mesfiwi, which takes the form of an immense courtyard (54x29m) paved in white marble and zellige and adorned with three fountains and surrounded by a portico of wooden shade with 52 fluted and painted columns. It serves as a courtyard for an imposing and resplendent hall of honour called the “Council room”.

It constitutes the largest room in the palace (20mx8), and stands out for its bay windows, its zellige and marble flooring, its sculpted plaster, its ceiling, its door leaves and its windows in painted cedar wood. It is the last room built at the palace following an inscription engraved on the right side of the entrance and on which we read the equivalent date of 1888-1889.